

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING
TOOLKIT FOR SYNERGISTIC INQUIRY REFLECTIVE
LEARNING (SIRL) STRATEGY**

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Development and Validation of a Self-Directed Learning Toolkit for Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) Strategy

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Abstract

This study aims to create and validate a learning toolkit that implements a new innovative teaching strategy called Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL). SIRL combines Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), and Reflection on Learning (RL) in one single approach for the General Education Course Science Technology and Society (STS). The toolkit consists of a Self-directed Learning Module, a Teacher's Guide, and Student Learning Sheets. The development process entailed meticulous proofreading, editing, and formatting to guarantee a user-friendly experience. The validation process involved the use of Rivera's Expert's Assessment Checklist to evaluate the toolkit based on its aims, content, organization, materials, resources, and efficacy. Experts evaluated all categories as "highly satisfactory" with an average score of 4.08. The inter-rater reliability was found to be high as evidenced by a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.925. The findings indicate that the toolkit is resilient, dependable, and successful in improving student engagement and learning achievements. The qualitative insights from student feedback highlighted themes of improved understanding, enhanced review and retention, increased engagement, and a balance between independence and collaboration. These findings underscore the practical consequences for wider educational implementations and propose that ongoing improvement guided by feedback will augment its efficacy. This research enhances the field by offering a verified groundbreaking educational tool that encourages profound learning and involvement through a comprehensive approach to teaching and learning.

Keywords: *Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL), learning toolkit validation, active learning strategies*

Introduction

It is crucial in modern education to foster deep and meaningful learning experiences by developing students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and reflecting skills. Many educators believe that traditional teaching methods, which often involve direct instruction and reliance on textbooks, may not effectively engage students or foster the interdisciplinary thinking required in today's complex world. This study aims to tackle this challenge by investigating the development and validation of a learning toolkit that is specifically designed to implement a comprehensive teaching approach known as Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL). The SIRL teaching strategy is a novel approach that brings together three engaging learning methods—Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), and Reflection on Learning (RL)—to provide a cohesive and enriching educational experience. Problem-Based Learning (PBL) emphasizes learning that is centered around the student. It involves tackling complex real-world problems that demand critical thinking and collaboration. This approach shifts the traditional focus from the teacher to the learner, encouraging teamwork and the practical application of knowledge. Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) aims to foster students' involvement in the scientific process by encouraging them to ask questions, carry out investigations, and reach conclusions based on evidence. This approach promotes curiosity, active learning, and a more profound comprehension of the subject matter. Reflection and Learning (RL) is all about students reflecting on their learning experiences, recognizing what they're good at and where they need to improve, and coming up with ways to get better. It helps them develop important skills for independent learning that they can use throughout their lives. The combination of these strategies in the SIRL framework aims to improve student engagement and learning outcomes by incorporating critical thinking, problem-solving, and reflective practices in a unified way. This combination tries to bring together the unique strengths of each strategy, resulting in a comprehensive and more effective educational approach. Although PBL, IBL, and RL have been acknowledged for their benefits, there is a scarcity of comprehensive studies that combine these strategies into one framework. Previous studies tend to only look at each approach separately without considering the possibility of producing positive effects that can occur when they are combined. Moreover, there is a lack of educational tools that have been validated and can help with the implementation of integrated strategies in interdisciplinary courses such as Science, Technology, and Society (STS). Thus, this study aims to address this issue by creating and validating a learning toolkit for the SIRL strategy. This toolkit will serve as a valuable resource for educators to improve student engagement and learning outcomes in a more connected and thoughtful way.

The General Education Course Science, Technology, and Society (STS) is a great fit for the SIRL strategy because it covers a wide range of topics and brings together different disciplines. This course requires students to understand and analyze how scientific progress, technological advancements, and societal consequences are all connected. When Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is incorporated, students have the opportunity to tackle real-life problems as a team and use critical thinking skills to come up with solutions. IBL improves this process by encouraging students to carefully analyze issues and scenarios, thus fostering a sense of curiosity and exploration. Reflective learning is a process that encourages students to think deeply and evaluate their own learning experiences. This helps them develop important skills like self-awareness and critical thinking, which are essential for ongoing learning throughout their lives. By incorporating these approaches into the SIRL framework, we expect that students will have better learning

experiences and achieve better outcomes.

A comprehensive learning toolkit was created to support the implementation of the SIRL teaching strategy. The toolkit consists of a Self-directed Learning Module, a Teacher's Guide, and Student Learning Sheets. The production process involved careful proofreading, editing, and formatting to ensure that the resources were easy to use and effective for both instructors and students. To ensure the quality and effectiveness of the toolkit, we conducted a comprehensive validation procedure using Rivera's Expert's Assessment Checklist. This checklist evaluated various aspects of the toolkit, including its objectives, content, organization, materials, resources, and overall effectiveness. The toolbox was improved even more by taking into account feedback from experts. The high validation ratings and strong inter-rater reliability results show that the toolkit is a reliable and dependable resource for enhancing student engagement and improving learning outcomes in the STS course. This study not only provides a reliable educational resource but also contributes to the broader field of educational research by demonstrating how integrated teaching strategies can transform teaching and learning practices.

Research Questions

This study aims to create and validate a learning toolkit that implements a teaching strategy called Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL). Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the expert evaluations of the learning toolkit in terms of objectives, content, organization, materials, resources, and overall effectiveness?
2. How reliable is the assessment of the learning toolkit's effectiveness based on inter-rater reliability measures, such as Cronbach's Alpha?
3. How effective is the Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) learning toolkit in enhancing student engagement and learning outcomes in the General Education Course Science, Technology, and Society (STS)?

Literature Review

Integration of Pedagogical Strategies

The integration of multiple pedagogical strategies, such as Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), and Reflection on Learning (RL), has been recognized as a powerful approach to enhancing educational outcomes. PBL, which originated in medical education, emphasizes student-centered learning through complex, real-world problems that require critical thinking and collaboration (Barrows, 1996). This method has been widely adopted across various disciplines, demonstrating its effectiveness in promoting deeper understanding and retention of knowledge (Hmelo-Silver, 2004). Similarly, IBL encourages students to explore and investigate questions, fostering a sense of curiosity and promoting active engagement with the learning material (Hmelo-Silver et al., 2007). Combining these strategies with Reflection on Learning (RL), which focuses on students' metacognitive processes and self-awareness of their learning, can create a synergistic effect that enhances overall educational experiences (Schön, 1983).

Problem-Based Learning (PBL)

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has been extensively studied and documented in educational research. Savery (2006) highlights that PBL not only develops problem-solving skills but also improves students' ability to apply knowledge in practical situations. This approach shifts the traditional teacher-centered paradigm to a learner-centered one, where students take responsibility for their learning. The collaborative nature of PBL also fosters essential skills such as teamwork, communication, and critical thinking. Research by Strobel and van Barneveld (2009) supports these findings, indicating that PBL can lead to better long-term retention and application of knowledge compared to traditional teaching methods.

Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL)

Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL) is another pedagogical approach that has gained prominence in education over time. According to Zion et al., 2012, IBL encourages students to engage in the scientific process, formulating questions, conducting investigations, and drawing conclusions based on evidence. This method promotes active learning and helps students better understand the subject matter. IBL is particularly effective in science education, where it helps students grasp complex concepts and develop critical thinking skills (Kuhlthau et al, 2015). The emphasis on inquiry and exploration aligns well with the goals of the STS course, making it a suitable component of the SIRL strategy.

Reflection on Learning (RL)

Reflection on Learning (RL) is a crucial aspect of the educational process that encourages students to think about their learning experiences, understand their strengths and weaknesses, and develop strategies for improvement. (Schön,1983) argues that reflective practice is essential for professional development and continuous learning. In the context of higher education, Reflection on Learning (RL) helps students develop metacognitive skills, which are critical for self-directed learning and lifelong education. Research by (Moon,1999) supports the notion that reflective activities can enhance learning outcomes by allowing students to make connections between theory and practice. Incorporating RL into the SIRL strategy ensures that students engage with the content and reflect on their

learning processes, leading to deeper and more meaningful learning experiences. RL, conversely, enables students to critically reflect on their learning experiences and the societal implications of scientific knowledge, further solidifying the interdisciplinary approach by integrating ethical considerations into the learning process (Aldo, 2018).

Synergistic Effects of Combined Strategies

The combination of PBL, IBL, and RL into a unified teaching strategy can create a comprehensive and engaging learning environment, hence the Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning. According to Dole et al. (2016), integrating multiple pedagogical approaches can address the diverse learning needs of students and promote a more holistic educational experience. This integrated approach leverages the strengths of each strategy, resulting in enhanced student engagement, motivation, and achievement. Research by Hmelo-Silver et al. (2007) indicates that such integrated strategies can lead to significant improvements in students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and inquiry skills. The development and validation of a learning toolkit that facilitates the implementation of the SIRL strategy represents a significant contribution to educational practice and research, providing educators with effective tools to enhance interdisciplinary learning in courses like STS.

Moreover, the inclusion of these pedagogical strategies aligns with the 21st-century Century Skills framework. The framework underscores the importance of critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration in preparing students for the complexities of the modern world (Partnership for 21st Century Skills, 2009) where it complements the interdisciplinary approach to STS by highlighting the skills and competencies necessary for students to navigate the challenges and opportunities presented by science and technology in society.

In summary, the literature supports the efficacy of PBL, IBL, and RL as individual pedagogical strategies and highlights the potential benefits of integrating these approaches. The development of the SIRL active teaching strategy and its corresponding learning toolkit is grounded in this rich body of research, aiming to create an innovative and effective educational framework. The validation of the toolkit by experts further reinforces its potential to transform teaching and learning practices, offering a robust resource for educators seeking to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes in interdisciplinary courses.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized a mixed-methods research design to develop and validate the learning toolkit for the Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) strategy in the General Education Course Science, Technology, and Society (STS). The mixed-methods approach combines quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis techniques, comprehensively evaluating the toolkit's effectiveness and reliability. The quantitative part of the study focused on the actual expert validation of the learning toolkit, while the qualitative portion of the study tried to capture the perceived effectiveness of the learning toolkit from the students who utilized the toolkit.

Participants

The main participants of this study were three (3) expert validators and the students enrolled in the GE Course Science Technology and Society who utilized the learning toolkit as their main learning material for the course. The three experts were selected based on their capability as developers of instructional materials and expertise with educational assessment and evaluation, along with their familiarity with STS as a course taught in the Tertiary General Education curricula.

Instruments

The researcher adapted Rivera's (2011) Expert's Assessment Checklist to evaluate the learning toolkit based on objectives, content, organization, materials and resources, and effectiveness. The experts' feedback was incorporated to refine the final version of the learning toolkit.

Procedure

The development of the learning toolkit dealt with the actual writing and production of the STS learning material which was composed of three items – the Self-directed Learning Module, the Teacher's Guide, and the Student Learning Sheets. These materials were utilized to facilitate the administration of PBL, IBL, and RL learning strategies in STS.

This stage included proofreading, editing, and reproduction. The learning materials were subjected to grammar and spelling checks on the computer with the help of grammar editing software while it was being encoded. After auto-editing, the text, graphics, formatting, and layout were carried out for the artistic appearance to make it more student and teacher-friendly.

Each expert verified the material using Rivera's (2011) Expert Assessment Checklist, which assessed objectives, content, organization, material and resources, and effectiveness. Experts' revision ideas guided the Learning Toolkit's final editing.

After the expert validation, 40 first-year students enrolled in the GE Course Science Technology and Society took a pre-test to determine their competency level before the learning toolkit was utilized during the pilot testing. The learning toolkit served as their main learning material for the course. Subsequently, the students took the post-test after completing the topics included in Unit I, which was the main

focus of the learning toolkit. The experiences and perceived effectiveness of the learning toolkit were also gathered from the students through a semi-structured interview after the post-test.

The results of the pretests and posttests in each learning module were subjected to paired sample z-test to identify the differences in the mean values of each test to tell whether the achievement level of the students had a significant effect after using the learning toolkit.

Ethical Considerations

Observing ethical standards in research is essential. At the core, this helped shape the true aims of the study, such as knowledge, truth, and avoidance of error, and promoted values essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. To ensure ethical research, the researcher sought permission from the administration of the State University where the study took place and moved through channels to conduct the study. Moreover, explicit informed consent was provided for the participant's awareness and permission to participate in the study specifically in the qualitative phase of the study. The researcher personally explained the study's nature and informed consent to the participants.

Results and Discussion

This section will present the quantitative and qualitative results of the study which highlights the effectiveness of the Self-Directed Learning Toolkit for Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) Teaching Strategy.

Table 1. Summary of Experts' Ratings on the Inquiry-Based Learning Modules

Criteria	Experts Individual Rating			Grand Mean	Verbal Description	Mean for Criterion
	1	2	3			
A. Objectives						
1. are clearly stated	5	4	5	4.67	Outstanding	
2. are attainable and measurable	5	4	4	4.33	Highly Satisfactory	4.33 (HS)
3. are exposed in terms of competencies which are knowledge, skills, and attitudes.	4	3	5	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
B. Content						
1. Provide a topic in the course outline	5	3	5	4.33	Highly Satisfactory	4.18 (HS)
2. is relevant to the learning activities	5	4	5	4.67	Outstanding	
3. provides sufficient information	5	4	3	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
4. features value-laden learning activities	5	3	3	3.67	Highly Satisfactory	
C. Organization						
1. the instructional material is simple and easy to follow	4	4	3	3.67	Highly Satisfactory	3.76 (HS)
2. instructions are clear and concise	4	4	3	3.67	Highly Satisfactory	
3. there is a systematic sequencing of the lesson	4	4	3	3.67	Highly Satisfactory	
4. the instructional material provides progression and consecutive depths of ideas	4	4	4	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
5. the instructional material is presented with a specific format and adapted to the overall style	4	3	4	3.67	Highly Satisfactory	
6. the instructional material provides adequate study aids such as questions, problems, and explorations	5	4	1	3.33	Satisfactory	
7. instructional events are relevant to objectives	5	4	4	4.33	Highly Satisfactory	
D. Materials and Resources						
1. various resources are tapped to widen access to knowledge to enrich learning	5	4	4	4.33	Highly Satisfactory	4.0 (HS)
2. materials provided are fitted to instructional event	5	4	3	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
3. students have pre-requisite skills to use the materials	4	4	3	3.67	Highly Satisfactory	
E. Effectivity						
1. the instructional materials can be used to guide students	5	4	5	4.67	Outstanding	4.17 (HS)
2. the instructional materials involve the students' active learning through appropriate activities	5	4	3	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
3. the instructional materials utilize practical application	5	4	3	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
4. the instructional material can motivate learning	5	4	3	4.00	Highly Satisfactory	
Overall Rating	4.67	3.81	3.76	4.03	Highly Satisfactory	

The experts were asked to validate the learning modules using the Experts' Assessment Checklist adapted from Rivera (2011) The summary of ratings is presented in Table 1. The mean rating for each criterion was computed by getting the average of the mean rating of the experts. The grand mean for each criterion was again computed to obtain the mean for each criterion.

The experts' ratings were also subject to the scales of internal consistency. This refers to the extent to which a test or procedure assesses the same characteristics, skills, and qualities. It measures precision between the objectives and the measuring instruments used in the study. This type of reliability often helps researchers interpret data, and predict the value of scores and the limits of relationship among variables. One of the most commonly used indicators of internal consistency is the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient. Ideally, the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient of states should be above 0.7.

Table 2. Summary of Inter-rater Reliability Test among Experts' Ratings

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N
Item Means	4.08	3.33	4.67	1.33	1.40	.151	.925	.939	20
Item Variances	.83	.33	4.33	4.00	13.00	.825			

To determine the inter-rater reliability, the responses of the experts on the 21 items in the assessment checklist were subjected to the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. However, the number of items in the computation was deemed 20 because the criterion regarding the learning toolkit providing progression and consecutive depths of ideas had the same ratings from all three experts. The overall value computed by getting the average value is 0.925, a value above the critical limit of 0.7 which indicates that there was a high agreement among experts. This result can be seen in the table below.

Table 3. Achievement Level of Students in the Pretest and Posttest during the Pilot Test

Pretest Posttest	Mean Difference	SD	t-value	Std. Error Mean	df	p-value (2-tailed)	Interpretation
Unit 1	-3.24	1.4	-14.55	0.22	40	.000	Highly Significant

The results of the pilot test reveal a significant difference in students' achievement levels between the pretest and posttest. For Unit 1, the mean difference was -3.24, with a standard deviation (SD) of 1.43. The t-value was -14.55, with a standard error mean of 0.22, and the degrees of freedom (df) were 40. The p-value (2-tailed) was .000, indicating that the difference was highly significant.

The qualitative data from student feedback reveals additional dimensions of the learning toolkit's effectiveness as summarized in the table below.

Table 4. Perceives Effectiveness of Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) Teaching Strategy

Themes	Sample Quoted Statements
Improved Understanding	"The lessons are easier to understand when there are learning modules. We have a reference especially since the subject is new to us." (P1) "I understood many of the lessons because there were suggested internet sites where we can browse additional readings when we go home from school." (P2) "Taking down notes is easier because the important details of the lessons are shown in the Key Concepts. Explanations are given also in this part so important things are easily remembered especially during exams or summative tests." (P5)
Enhanced Review and Retention	"The topics are easier to understand compared to the first weeks of the semester because we can revisit and review what we have already studied. Reviewing is easier." (P3) "Taking down notes is easier because the important details of the lessons are shown in the Key Concepts. Explanations are given also in this part so important things are easily remembered especially during exams." (P4)
Increased Engagement	"We enjoyed the activities. The class is not boring because everyone is doing something." (P2) "The learning modules helped us to be more independent but at the same time helped us to work with our classmates. Even though sometimes we argue with our groupmates during activities, we are able to solve the tasks given to us." (P3)
Independence and Collaboration	"The learning modules in the toolkit helped us to be more independent but at the same time helped us to work with our classmates." (P1) "Even though sometimes we argue with our groupmates during activities, we are able to solve the tasks given to us in the learning sheets." (P3)

These themes highlight how learning toolkits contribute to students' understanding, retention, engagement, and collaborative skills, showcasing their overall effectiveness in enhancing the educational experience.

The evaluations of the Self-Directed Learning Toolkit for Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) Teaching Strategy by the experts were very positive. Table 1 provides a summary of these ratings, showing that there is strong approval across various criteria. The modules' objectives received high marks, with an average rating of 4.33. The experts agree that the objectives were clearly stated, achievable, and measurable. They also reflected well-defined competencies in knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The content was also well received, with an average rating of 4.18. Experts specifically mentioned that the topics were relevant and that there was enough information provided. However, they did suggest that there could be some improvement in integrating activities that promote values development.

The instructional modules included in the toolkit were considered to be simple and easy to follow in terms of organization. They provided clear instructions and followed a systematic sequence. The average score for this criterion was 3.76, indicating that it is generally effective. However, there is still room for improvement, especially in providing better study aids. The materials and resources including online links were highly rated, with an average score of 4.00. They were appreciated for their variety and appropriateness. On the other hand, it was observed that students may require additional prerequisite skills to make the most of these resources.

The instructional materials were found to be highly effective, receiving an average rating of 4.17. Experts emphasized their importance in guiding students, promoting active learning, facilitating practical application, and enhancing motivation. The high ratings show how the learning modules have a real impact on student engagement and learning outcomes. The experts gave the modules an overall rating of 4.03, which is classified as "Highly Satisfactory." This indicates that the experts had a generally positive assessment of the modules.

When it comes to internal consistency and reliability, it is important to ensure that the data and measurements used are consistent and reliable.

The ratings provided by the experts seen in Table 2 were tested for consistency among different raters using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. The test yielded a value of 0.925. The high value indicates that the experts strongly agree, which confirms that the ratings provided are reliable. Consistency is really important because it helps make sure that the evaluations are trustworthy and accurately reflect how effective the learning toolkits are.

The results of the pilot test show that there was a noticeable improvement in the students' achievement levels from the beginning of the test to the end. In Unit 1, the average difference was -3.24, and the variability was measured by a standard deviation of 1.43. The calculated t-value was -14.55, indicating a strong effect. The standard error mean was 0.22, suggesting a relatively small amount of variability in the data. The analysis was based on a sample size of 40, providing a sufficient number of degrees of freedom for reliable results. The p-value (two-tailed) was 0.000, suggests that the difference was extremely significant. Thus, the results show that the Self-Directed Learning Toolkit for SIRL teaching strategy has a significant positive effect on how well students learn.

Based on the feedback from students, it is clear that the learning toolkit is effective. This is supported by qualitative data gathered from the semi-structured interview. From the feedback, four key themes emerged. These include better comprehension, improved ability to review and remember information, increased involvement, and finding a good balance between working independently and collaborating with others. The students liked how clear and thorough the learning modules included in the toolkit were. Students said that it made it easier for them to understand and remember the lessons. The interactive activities and collaborative tasks were really engaging, which made the learning experience enjoyable and effective.

Overall, the findings from both quantitative and qualitative analysis suggest that the Self-Directed Learning Toolkit for Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) Teaching Strategy is generally effective. The ratings from experts, the consistent results, the noticeable improvement in student achievement, and the positive feedback from students all show that the toolkit can make education better by helping students understand, remember, participate, and work together.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study was able to create and confirm the effectiveness of a Learning toolkit that implements a new innovative active teaching and learning pedagogy. The toolkit is designed to support the Synergistic Inquiry Reflective Learning (SIRL) strategy, which combines Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Inquiry-Based Learning (IBL), and Reflection on Learning (RL) into one single approach. The toolkit received high ratings from experts in terms of meeting objectives, content quality, organization, materials, and overall effectiveness. The strong inter-rater reliability, indicated by a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.925, further supports these positive evaluations. The quantitative data revealed that there were notable improvements in student achievement. On average, there was a difference of -3.24 between the scores of the pretest and posttest. The qualitative feedback emphasized that the participants experienced improved understanding, better retention of information, increased engagement, and enhanced collaborative skills. These findings confirm that the toolkit is effective in promoting active learning and improving educational outcomes in interdisciplinary courses such as Science, Technology, and Society (STS). Therefore, this study offers a valuable resource for educators, showing the importance of incorporating interactive and reflective strategies to promote more meaningful learning and student engagement.

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